

ROLE OF ELECTRONIC CATALOGS IN LIBRARIES IN INTELLECTUALIZATION OF INFORMATION SEARCH ACTIVITY

Ro'ziyeva Nilufar

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7493889>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21st December 2022

Accepted: 29th December 2022

Online: 30th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Electronic catalog, new generation catalogs, library users, information-search languages, library services, access points, digital information.

ABSTRACT

The article reveals the problem of the functioning of the library's electronic catalogs during the emergence and formation of new generation systems that provide intellectualization of the information retrieval process. Study of the role and influence of the electronic catalog on the information environment in the newly created library, analysis of its functionality in the perspective of using new technological and software tools and services in its work. The development of various information programs both for society as a whole and for libraries will inevitably lead to an increase in the level of requirements for both librarians and library development. One of the main directions of using new technologies in the library is the electronic catalog.

The high rate of development of the information society requires adaptation to new trends, implementation of modern technologies, rapid growth of the digital content market. The introduction of new formats and methods of participation of libraries in educational activities is connected with the emergence of information and communication technologies. The existence of the "Yangi Avlod" library and its information resources is determined, first of all, by the technological environment adopted at the current stage and the professional principles of building such a library. Speaking about the technological environment, it should be noted that for almost the last ten years, the library team of Uzbekistan has been studying and

testing new technological solutions in library practice. The beginning of this process is connected with the rapid development of ICT. In fact, from the 90s of the 20th century, the libraries of Uzbekistan began to actively use computer technology and Internet technologies in their work. The role and place of libraries in the modern information society is no longer determined by the number of documents in the fund, but by the level of service to users. is determined. Currently, libraries must compete with other information intermediaries and take into account the existence of competitors such as digital libraries and databases, as well as Internet search engines. In general, the demands of modern users on libraries can be described as maximum attention to

accessibility and results. Traditional library equipment is not enough to meet these requirements. Libraries are forced to change the entire paradigm of their activity with one goal - to find their place in the digital world and to be in demand in the new information society. With the availability and active use of information technologies, the boundaries between the concepts of "scientific" and "public" (public) libraries, the information capabilities of libraries that differ fundamentally in terms of the size of document arrays stored in them, began to blur.

At the moment, the difficulties encountered by library users in searching for information from electronic catalogs have been identified. There is a mismatch between users' high demands and expectations for electronic catalogs and their existing search capabilities. The development of a multi-format media environment necessitated the improvement of search tools, which led to the emergence of a new generation of library catalogs. The possible prospects of electronic catalogs as a single point of access for users to library resources are considered in order to implement new search mechanisms.

These problems are solved by libraries using modern and effective means of providing library services in the electronic space, including: electronic catalog (EC) and virtual reference service, digitized collections, personal user accounts, electronic notification system for private users, electronic catalogs of network resources. In fact, it is traditional elements for the library, but presented in a new environment and has radically new possibilities. Of all the above set of tools, EC

is the priority, because it is the basis of all information-bibliographic services and is responsible for the efficiency of the library. Entering the Internet environment, libraries are trying to maximize their resources for readers through the electronic catalog. In the current situation, we can talk about the effectiveness of the search process only in terms of how successfully this catalog (or another search system) allows you to quickly find the desired document.

The scientific novelty of the work is as follows:

- An analysis of the electronic catalog, the main electronic information resource of the newly established library, was conducted. In the conditions where there is no traditional card catalog in the library and all technological directions of the work are initially organized in an automated mode, it is the subject of determining its special status and role in the processes of forming the information environment;
- The information environment of the "Yangi Avlod" library was comprehensively studied, its characteristics and principles of organization were presented, new forms of information services created in the resource base of the electronic catalog were identified, and readers interact with this information resource through them.
- New Web-technology services used in open systems of electronic catalogs, capable of influencing the status characteristics of the library and its users, are separately identified and described;
- Methods of obtaining statistical indicators based on the electronic catalog collected in the process of library services are the richest basis for choosing optimal management decisions and scientifically based library management.

At the same time, it should be noted that there are a number of problems that have been clearly identified during the operation of the electronic catalog. The main problem covered in the articles of E. R. Sukiasyan [1; 2] and IS Skripkin [3] lack of uniform rules and principles for building electronic catalogs. This situation makes it difficult for librarians to switch from one program to another, so mistakes are made at the stage of entering the bibliographic description into the system. But the human factor affects the search engine not only by librarians, but also by users. Now, all libraries are trying to simplify the search by introducing a "one-stop shop" system. It seems easier for users.

In their publications, foreign authors present a list of characteristics of the information behavior of young people, which include:

- 1) the desire to get a single resource such as Amazon or Google that provides instant results;
- 2) library databases seem too complicated for young people due to the use of logical operations in them;
- 3) young people use the Internet by trial and error and ignore tutorials and advice[4].

Library electronic catalogs are not easy to use. In addition, each automated library system has its own interface, its own search rules, and official keyword searches are sometimes so loose that a person gets a lot of information noise. If we take into account the fact that not everyone can correctly formulate a request for information, often the search results are reduced to almost zero. What to do in this situation? I. L. Shreiberg, in his speech at the annual conference "Crimea" on the topic "Modern libraries under the pressure

of information technologies on the thorny road to the future: the history of the "struggle with the book" and its prospects for survival" I. urged libraries to live in accordance with the rules of this environment and to do so as soon as possible an information technology environment that enables adaptation. Among them, new generation web platforms (Internet services that develop web 2.0 capabilities) stand out; "open mobile platforms and mobile communication; modern tools and systems for organizing and storing information, as well as access to it, including "computing clouds" and semantic search; electronic resources, including electronic full-text collections and digital libraries" [5, p. 32].

Library-information service in the 21st century will have its own characteristics of library work and the expansion of library services, including: "the use of multi-format media environment and the provision of documents to users. various tools (Internet section, film, sound recording, microfiche, etc.); work on unified information flow systems in various libraries and information systems, including organizing search using a new class of systems such as "Discovery"; providing automated translation, especially given the expansion of English-language content (full-text subscriptions), etc. [5, p. 46].

Thus, the need to change the tools that provide users with information resources and their search becomes clear. Between 2005 and 2007, OCLC conducted a series of studies [6, 7, 8] aimed at understanding how users evaluate library systems, information services, and access to research information. As a result of the research, recommendations were offered,

many of which related to changes in search tools, the basis of which is EC in libraries. In the early 2000s, working to improve the search capabilities of electronic directories in the United States. led to the emergence of a new generation of library catalogs, which was called the "next generation catalog" ("new generation catalogs"). In addition to this phrase, periodicals use concepts such as catalog 2.0, OPAC 2.0, third generation catalog, etc. Ch Hildreth's research [9; 10] led him to develop his own version of the directory ("the third generation directory"), where he paid special attention to functional improvements, among which the following can be noted: formulating a query to the system in natural language, sorting search results . , selection of bibliographic entries by relevance ("more similar", "not interesting"), tracking user preferences and various options for helping the user (check spelling of words, work with synonyms, automatically translate terms change).

The term "Next Generation Cataloging" was coined by Marshall Breeding in his article "Next Generation Library Cataloging" [11]. In it, he gives the characteristic features of new generation electronic catalogs. Let's take a closer look at some of them. The new generation EC should use more complete information than traditional catalogs using data from external sources. For example, the content of online bookstores (books,

magazines, multimedia products, images, etc.) or additional web applications (cumulative reviews, summaries, brief comments, etc.). In addition, he calls the possibility of significantly expanding the information space available for searching as the most important feature of the new generation catalog. Thus, EC becomes a single point of access to all library and bibliographic information available in the library (electronic collections, full-text databases to which the library has licensed access).

This feature is the weak point of all new generation ECs available in the network today. This feature is not fully implemented in any of the systems under consideration. Bibliographic services and search tools do not stand still, they are constantly being improved, showing their importance and relevance. New information systems, such as the new generation EC, have great potential and can change the nature of user interaction with the ever-expanding information space. The capabilities of new search tools often exceed the level of knowledge of users who are used to working with Yandex and Google. For such individuals, libraries should help expand their knowledge. And the library staff should improve their working methods and technologies in order to realize all the advantages of the new systems of using information resources.

References:

1. Сукиасян Э.Р. За что читатели любили систематический каталог? Научные и технические библиотеки. 2014; 5: 45 – 51.
2. Сукиасян Э.Р. Классификационная система как инструмент автоматизированного поиска. Ч. 1. Почему классификационный поиск эффективнее вербального? Научные и технические библиотеки. 2015; 3: 20 – 29.

3. Скрипкина И.С. Функциональность электронного каталога следует изучать Научные и технические библиотеки. 2014; 5: 52 – 55.
4. Веб 2.0, библиотеки и информационная грамотность: сборник публикаций. Перевод с английского. Санкт-Петербург: Профессия, 2011.
5. Шрайберг Я.Л. Современные библиотеки под информационно-технологическим прессингом на тернистом пути в будущее: история «борьбы» с книгой и перспективы ее выживания»: ежегодный доклад Конференции «Крым», год 2015. Москва: ГПНТБ России, 2015.
6. College Students' Perceptions of Libraries and Information Resources: A Report to the OCLC Membership. Dublin, Ohio: 2006. Режим доступа: <http://www.oclc.org/reports/perceptionscollege.htm>
7. Perceptions of Libraries and Information Resources : A Report to the OCLC Membership. Dublin, Ohio, 2005. Режим доступа: <http://www.oclc.org/reports/2005perceptions.htm>
8. The 2003 OCLC environmental scan: pattern recognition. Dublin: OCLC. Режим доступа: http://www.oclc.org/reports/escan/downloads/escansummary_en.pdf
9. Hildreth C. R. Online Catalog Design Models: Are We Moving in the Right Direction? Режим доступа: <http://myweb.cwpost.liu.edu/childret/clr-opac.html>
10. Hildreth C. R. Online library catalogs as IR systems: what can we learn from research?" In Yates-Mercer, P.A. (Ed.), Future Trends in Information Science and Technology: Proceedings of the Silver Jubilee Conference of the City University's Department of Information Science, Taylor Graham. London, 1998: 9 – 25.
11. Breeding M. Next-Generation Library Catalogs. Chapter 1: Introduction Library Technology Reports. 2007. 43, 4. P. 5–14. Available at: <http://alatechsource.metapress.com/content/p6r112h042601168/fulltex>